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ANOMALY DETECTION FOR MULTIVARIATE TIME SERIES
IN WATER DISTRIBUTION IOT SYSTEMS

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Abstract

Water is a common good and a limited and strategic resource that needs to be protected and used in a sustainable way, in terms of both quality and quantity. Water resources are under unprecedented stress levels because of the combination of demographic evolution, the general trend of increasing urbanisation, and the impacts of climate change. These conditions force water operators to manage the water demand sustainably and efficiently, identify and manage water leakages properly, and prioritise the assets' rehabilitation in order to guarantee human welfare.

In the last few years, ICT (Information and Communication Technologies) greatly improved and matured, producing novel data-based methodologies, new devices, and smart Decision Support Systems (DSS) to help improve water resource management in man-made or natural environments, especially regarding monitoring and reporting quality, quantity, reuse of water, extreme events, and leakages.

Some front-runner water utilities have already put into practise new digital technologies, such as smart sensors and actuators, drones and robots, and advanced data analytics models that provide detailed data, allowing deeper insights into water availability, quality, and use down to the level of each individual user.

In particular, many water distribution networks (WDNs) are continuously monitored through installed sensors that measure hydraulic parameters and water quality parameters. This continuous monitoring allows the collection of raw data to be used in multiple engineering applications, with flow rate and pressure data being the most widely used time series by water utilities. The success of most tools strongly depends on the existence of well-processed, reliable, and synchronised time series.

Performing leakage control, detecting changes in customer water demand or manoeuvring in the network can be summarised as physical anomaly detection. To perform this task, the time series of flow rate and pressure need to be analysed and passed through an anomaly detection model.

The aim of this work is to create an anomaly detection model based on semi-supervised methods of deep learning to discover both sensor anomalies, caused by malfunctions and failures of the devices or of the logging system, and physical anomalies.

Sommario

L'acqua è un bene comune e una risorsa limitata e strategica, che necessita di protezione e di venir utilizzata in maniera sostenibile in termini di qualità e quantità. Le risorse idriche sono sotto livelli di stress senza precedenti per via della combinazione di sviluppo demografico, l'aumento generale dell'urbanizzazione e gli impatti del cambiamento climatico. Queste condizioni obbligano gli operatori idrici a curare la domanda d'acqua in maniera sostenibile ed efficiente, a identificare e gestire propriamente le perdite d'acqua, e a dare priorità alla riabilitazione delle risorse per garantire il benessere umano.

Negli ultimi anni, l'ICT (Information and Communication Technologies) è fortemente avanzato, producendo nuove metodologie guidate dai dati, nuovi device e smart Decision Support Systems (DSS) per aiutare per migliorare la gestione delle risorse idriche sia in ambienti artificiali che naturali, specialmente per quanto riguarda il monitoraggio e la segnalazione di qualità, quantità, il riutilizzo d'acqua, eventi estremi (inondazioni o siccità) e perdite.

Qualche azienda di erogazione idrica all'avanguardia ha già messo in pratica nuove tecnologie digitali, come sensori smart, droni, robot e modelli avanzati di analisi dati che forniscono dati dettagliati, permettendo analisi approfondite su disponibilità dell'acqua, qualità e utilizzo, fino al livello del singolo utente.

In particolare, molte reti di distribuzione idrica sono continuamente monitorate tramite sensori installati, i quali misurano parametri idraulici e di qualità dell'acqua. Questo monitoraggio continuo permette di raccogliere dati grezzi da utilizzare in varie applicazioni ingegneristiche, con portata e pressione le due serie temporali più utilizzate dai servizi idrici in diverse applicazioni. Il successo della maggior parte di questi strumenti dipende dall'esistenza di serie temporali ben processate, affidabili e sincronizzate.

Svolgere controllo di perdite, rilevare cambi nelle utenze o manovre nella rete può venire riassunto sotto l'azione di rilevamento di anomalie fisiche. Per svolgere questo compito, le serie temporali di portata e pressione devono venire analizzate e passate attraverso un modello per la rilevazione di anomalie.

Lo scopo di questo lavoro di tesi è di creare tale modello per la rilevazione di anomalie basata su metodi di deep learning semi-supervisionati, volto a trovare nella rete di approvvigionamento idrico sia anomalie di sensore, dovute a malfunzionamenti o guasti dei device o del sistema di registrazione, che anomalie fisiche.

Contents

Abstract	i
Sommario	ii
List of Figures	vi
List of Acronyms	vii
1 Introduction	1
1.1 Thesis structure	5
2 Anomaly detection	6
2.1 Definition of anomaly	6
2.2 Types of anomalies	7
2.3 Nature of input data	9
2.4 Output	11
2.5 Data labels	11
2.6 Challenges	12
2.7 Applications	13
2.8 Anomaly detection in WDS	14
3 Deep anomaly detection models	22
3.1 Deep learning architectures	23
3.1.1 RNNs	24
3.1.2 Variations of CNNs	29
3.1.3 Transformer	33
3.2 Error evaluation	34
3.2.1 Metrics	35
3.3 Anomaly detection model definition	37
3.4 Training the models	39

3.5	Hyperparameter tuning	41
4	The data set	45
4.1	Correlation	46
4.2	Preprocessing	47
4.2.1	Data normalisation	47
4.2.2	Feature engineering	48
4.3	Sensor anomalies	49
4.4	Physical anomalies	50
5	Results	53
5.1	Model architecture selection	53
5.2	Model application	55
5.2.1	Measurement zone A	56
5.2.2	Measurement zone B	58
5.2.3	Measurement zone C	60
6	Conclusions and future work	62
	Bibliography	64
	Appendix A Implementation	72
A.1	Python packages	72

List of Figures

2.1	Example of point anomaly.	7
2.2	Example of contextual anomaly.	8
2.3	Example of collective anomaly.	9
2.4	Example of multivariate time series.	10
2.5	WSS sketch.	15
2.6	Macroindicators ARERA	17
2.7	Performance class of the WSN according to water leakages.	18
2.8	Goals to be achieved according to the performance class of the WSS.	18
2.9	IWA's strategies for water losses management.	19
3.1	Architecture of a RNN.	24
3.2	Architecture of a RNN block.	25
3.3	Architecture of a LSTM block.	26
3.4	Architecture of a GRU block.	28
3.5	Architecture of a CNN.	29
3.6	Architecture of CNN-LSTM.	31
3.7	Architecture of a TCN.	32
3.8	Architecture of a Transformer.	34
3.9	Comparison between error metrics.	37
3.10	Anomaly index distribution with threshold.	38
3.11	Example of sliding window method.	41
3.12	Example of Bayesian Optimisation procedure.	44
4.1	Example of time series in data set.	45
4.2	Normalised time series, to show correlation.	46
4.3	Example of sensor anomaly.	50
4.4	Example of physical anomaly.	51
4.5	Data set division.	51
5.1	Results - MZ A.	56

5.2	Results - MZ A, sensor anomalies.	56
5.3	Results - MZ A, physical anomalies.	57
5.4	Results - MZ B.	58
5.5	Results - MZ B, sensor anomalies.	58
5.6	Results - MZ B, physical anomalies.	59
5.7	Results - MZ C.	60
5.8	Results - MZ C, sensor anomalies.	60
5.9	Results - MZ C, physical anomalies.	61

List of Acronyms

Adam:	Adaptive Moment estimation
AE:	Absolute Error
AI:	Artificial Intelligence
ALC:	Active Leakage Control
APE:	Absolute Percentage Error
ARERA:	Autorità di Regolazione per Energia Reti e Ambiente (Italian Regulatory Authority for Energy, Networks and Environment)
AWWA:	American Water Works Association
BO:	Bayesian Optimisation
BPTT:	Back Propagation Through Time
CNN:	Convolutional Neural Network
COP:	Conference of the Parties
DMA:	District Metered Areas
DNN:	Deep Neural Network
DSS:	Decision Support System
ECG:	Electrocardiogram
EEG:	Electroencephalogram
EGA:	Ente Governo d'Ambito
GP:	Gaussian Process
GRU:	Gated Recurrent Unit
ICT:	Information and Communication Technologies
IWA:	International Water Association
LSTM:	Long Short Term Memory
MLP:	Multilayer Perceptron
MSA:	Multihead Self-Attention
MSE:	Mean Squared Error
NLP:	Natural Language Processing
OECD:	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
ReLU:	Rectified Linear Unit

RNN: Recurrent Neural Network
RQTI: Regolazione della Qualità Tecnica del servizio Idrico (regulation for technical quality of the integrated water service)
sAPE: Symmetric Absolute Percentage Error
s2APE: Symmetric Symmetric Absolute Percentage Error
SCADA: Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition
SGD: Stochastic Gradient Descent
TCN: Temporal Convolutional Network
UN: United Nations
UCB: Upper Confidence Bound
WDN: Water Distribution Network
WDS: Water Distribution System
WSS: Water Supply System

Chapter 1

Introduction

“Water is the driving force of all nature”, stated Leonardo Da Vinci, the Italian genius of Science and Art highlighting the importance of such precious resource: water is essential for human, animal and plant life and for the economy.

Water is not a commercial product but a common good and a limited and strategic resource that needs to be protected and used in a sustainable way, in terms of both quality and quantity. Water resources, though, are under unprecedented stress levels because of the combination of demographic evolution, the general trend of increasing urbanisation, and the impacts of climate change. These conditions make the general scenario the water operators are working in even more multifaceted, especially when it comes to managing the water demand sustainably and efficiently, identifying and managing water leakages properly, checking the water quality supplied to the customers and prioritising the assets’ rehabilitation in order to safeguard human welfare [1].

Accessible and high-quality freshwater is a limited and highly variable resource: currently around the world 2.2 billion people do not have access to drinking water and basic water services. Two-thirds of the global population (4.0 billion people) live under conditions of severe water scarcity for at least 1 month of the year [2]. Nearly half of those people live in India and China. Half a billion people in the world face severe water scarcity all year round [3]. OECD (Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development) projections show that 40% of the world’s population currently lives in water-stressed river basins, and that water demand will rise by 55% by 2050 [4].

New strategies are needed for water conservation, improving water management, and enhancing the water supply systems’ resiliency in order to enjoy in the future a similar standard of living, especially in the territories with

a stronger vulnerability to water scarcity both in terms of quantity and quality. Saving water leaked from a Water Distribution System (WDS) represents one way of improving things. Timely detection of pipe burst and leakage events provides opportunities for water companies not only to save water but also money, energy, and their carbon footprint and to improve operational efficiency and customer service [5].

In the last few years, ICT (Information and Communication Technologies) greatly improved and matured, with a massive production of novel data-based methodologies, new devices, and smart Decision Support Systems (DSS), becoming key enablers to face water challenges. In particular, ICT solutions help greatly improve water resource management in man-made or natural environments, especially regarding monitoring and reporting quality, quantity, reuse of water, extreme events (floods and water scarcity), and leakages. This increases awareness of the true value of water by all stakeholders, in line with the UN Sustainable Development Goals, Paris Agreement and UN COP.

The water industry of the future is expected to be smart and resource-efficient, with networked, intelligent systems helping make better use of energy, avoid unnecessary water losses, and optimise the consumption of resources. Nevertheless, despite a promising technological scenario, the water domain is currently characterised by a low level of maturity concerning the standardisation of ICT solutions, their business processes, and their related implementation in the legislative framework. This is due to the fragmentation of the sector: no holistic vision being set out and a lack of integration and standardisation of the technology [6].

Some front-runner water utilities have already put into practise new digital technologies in an all-connected world, such as smart sensors and actuators, drones and robots, and advanced data analytics models that provide detailed data, allowing deeper insights into water availability, quality, and use down to the level of each individual user, intertwining all water processes involved and making “Digital Water” real.

In particular, many water distribution networks (WDNs) are continuously monitored through installed sensors that measure hydraulic parameters (e.g., flow rate, pressure, users’ consumption) and water quality parameters (e.g., chlorine concentration, pH, temperature).

This continuous monitoring allows the collection of raw data to be used in multiple engineering applications. Flow rate and pressure data are the most widely used time series by water utilities in applications such as: leakage control

(IWA); the optimisation of Water Distribution System segmentation [7, 8]; the calculation of water balances [9]; the evaluation of water supply system (WSS) key performance indicators [10]; the development and calibration of hydraulic models in terms of nodal demands and pipe roughness coefficients [11, 12, 13]; the application of burst detection and location techniques [14, 15, 16, 17]; the DMA water demand reconstruction [18] and forecast [19, 20, 21]. *Kossieris et al.* [22] focused on using smart metering technologies to minimize water losses and energy consumption also using users' measurements.

The success of most engineering tools strongly depends on the existence of well-processed, reliable, and synchronised time series for flow rate and pressure. The flow rate data are usually collected and stored at a regular pre-defined time-step, that ranges between 5 and 15 minutes. Unfortunately, not all sensors collect and transmit data at a regular time-step, such as impulse flow rate meters that register data when a fixed water volume passes through the meter: in these cases, unevenly spaced flow rate time series are obtained, with an irregular interval between measurements. Most engineering tools for water distribution systems require evenly spaced time series. Thus, a time-step normalisation is usually required depending on the acquisition and transmission settings.

Also, battery failure, inadequate acquisition range (e.g., above or below meter range or bidirectional flow) and data storage limitations may cause other sensor or logger errors [23, 24]. Regardless of the acquisition and transmission settings, the obtained raw flow rate time series may contain measurement errors, such as missing, repetitive or even false readings due to lack of sensor reliability, e.g. offset, drift or breakdowns [25, 26]. Common problems in real-world water network operation, affecting the communication system between sensors and data loggers or in the telecontrol system itself, often arise from generating missing data during certain periods of time. Furthermore, SCADA and telemetry systems generate extremely timewise heterogeneous data.

The unreliable data, typically known as outliers or anomalous values [27] should be detected and replaced before they can be used in engineering applications (e.g., hydraulic modeling, calibration, leak detection) [5] that support the network water management tasks, planning, investment plans, maintenance operations, billing/consumer services and operational control. Gaps of non-validated measurements must be reconstructed with estimated data, being different methods used to this purpose [28]. Additionally, that flow rate time series usually present daily and weekly patterns, which must be considered by the used reconstruction techniques [29, 27, 30]. Processing raw flow rate time

series (prior to any use by engineering tools) is crucial to guaranteeing reliable data that do not compromise the success of the ensuing engineering applications. Data processing aims at identifying and removing outliers, normalising the time-step and filling gaps with estimated values. Often, this time series processing is carried out manually, ultimately limiting the amount of data that can be simultaneously treated [31].

New approaches for time series validation and reconstruction are needed in order to support the engineering applications that will benefit from the foreseen swelling of data being generated today by environmental monitoring and utility infrastructures, amounting to thousands of terabytes in the future [6]. The validated time series will be the basis for new approaches aimed at more sustainable water use.

These new approaches started with the adoption of general statistical methods to discover patterns and trends in data, which were achieved through the creation and fitting of project-specific probability models. However, these techniques do not scale well with the amount of data and can become exceedingly slow for the needs of most application fields. A solution is the adoption of artificial intelligence, in particular of machine learning.

Machine learning is the use of mathematical and or statistical models to obtain a general understanding of the data to make predictions. In contrast to statistical approaches, its general-purpose algorithms are able to analyse rich and unwieldy data by learning from the input only, making it a more suitable method for the analysis of large amounts of information in a contained amount of time.

Machine learning forecasting proved to be very effective in capturing patterns in sequences of both structured and unstructured data, representing the perfect candidate for time-dependent data instances such as time series.

Time series are analysed to determine the long-term trend so as to forecast the future or perform some other form of analysis. This is used in many applications other than water supply networks, such as economic forecasting, workload projections, utility studies, weather forecasting, and any domain which involves temporal measurements.

Anomaly detection, a.k.a. outlier detection, is one of the most important data analysis tasks, making it a lasting yet active research area in various research communities for several decades, with early exploration dating back as far as to 1960s [32]. This task is of utmost importance also in time series analysis, where an anomaly often results in economic losses or damages to goods.

1.1 Thesis structure

This thesis focuses on the task of creating an anomaly detection pipeline based on semi-supervised methods of deep learning to discover both sensor anomalies, caused by malfunctions and failures, and physical anomalies, such as leakages or changes in customer water demand, in the water supply network.

In this first chapter, a comprehensive introduction was given to the topic of water distribution systems and the role of anomaly detection in them, providing the general context connected to this work.

The second chapter firstly provides a broad introduction to anomaly detection in a general setting. This includes defining the possible types of anomalies that can be encountered in data and the categorisation of techniques to detect them, while providing examples of applications and important challenges that are faced. Secondly, a more specific view of anomaly detection in water distribution systems is discussed.

The third chapter introduces the system used to detect anomalies through deep neural networks. The five network architectures considered in this work are described, along with possible techniques to tune their hyperparameters. Moreover, a selection of existing error metrics are analysed, and a new one is proposed. Lastly, a description of the model training procedure is given.

The next chapter describes a data set from a water supply network on which the whole work is based. In particular, it details the two types of anomalies to be identified in it and how the anomaly detection model was applied to perform the task.

Finally, results are presented and discussed, with the presentation of the results from the produced anomaly detection model applied to three measurement zones of the considered water supply network.

Lastly, conclusions are made, with some proposals for future work.

Chapter 2

Anomaly detection

This chapter identifies and discusses the different aspects of anomaly detection. A specific formulation is determined by several different factors, such as the nature of the input data, the availability of labels, as well as the constraints and requirements of the application domain.

As anticipated, this thesis will focus on time series. However, this chapter discusses the anomaly detection problem from a general point of view, as the thesis will move to specific methods in a later chapter. Now, a categorisation of anomalies and of input data is introduced, as well as three possible ways to exploit preexisting information on data abnormality in order to learn future behaviour. Then, a few challenges faced when approaching the problem are discussed, and some examples of applications are given. Lastly, the motivations and specifics of anomaly detection in water distribution systems are presented.

2.1 Definition of anomaly

Anomaly detection refers to the problem of finding patterns in data that do not conform to expected behaviour. These non-conforming patterns are often referred to as *anomalies*, *outliers*, *discordant observations*, *exceptions*, *peculiarities* or *contaminants* in different application domains. Of these, anomalies and outliers are two terms used most commonly in the context of anomaly detection, sometimes interchangeably [33].

Anomalies might be induced in the data for a variety of reasons, but they all have the common characteristic that they are interesting to the analyst. The real-life relevance of anomalies is a key feature of anomaly detection.

2.2 Types of anomalies

Anomalies can be classified into the following three categories [33]. All images are taken from [34].

Point anomalies. If an individual data instance can be considered as anomalous with respect to the rest of data, then the instance is defined as a *point anomaly*. This is the simplest type of anomaly and is the focus of the majority of research on anomaly detection.

These point anomalies may represent statistical noise, they could be produced by faulty sensing equipment or they could represent a significant short period event which is of interest to the operators of the system.

In Figure 2.1, an abstract example. The plot represents values of a random Gaussian noise with a point anomaly at step 1500, circled in red for easy identification.

As a real-life example, consider credit card fraud detection. Let the data set correspond to an individual’s credit card transactions. A transaction for which the amount spent is very high compared to the normal range for that person will be a point anomaly.

Figure 2.1: A point anomaly, circled in red, in random Gaussian noise.

Contextual anomalies. If a data instance is anomalous in a specific context, but not otherwise, then it is termed as a *contextual anomaly* (also referred to as *conditional anomaly* [35]). The notion of a context is inferred by the structure of the data set and needs to be specified when formulating the problem.

A data instance might be a contextual anomaly in a given context, but an identical instance could be considered in the norm in another context. In order to identify the context itself, *contextual attributes* are needed, to determine the neighbourhood of that instance. For example, in time series data, time is a contextual attribute which determines the position of an instance on the entire sequence.

An example of contextual anomaly can be found in temperature time series, which show the monthly temperature of an area over time. A temperature of 8°C might be normal during winter, but the same value during summer would be an anomaly.

A more theoretical example is in Figure 2.2, which represents a sin wave with an anomalous instance. The value at sample 600 belongs to the function domain and is the same as a number of other observations however, in that context, it is considered an anomaly.

The choice of using a contextual anomaly detection technique is determined by the meaningfulness of the contextual anomalies in the application domain, and on the availability of contextual attributes.

Figure 2.2: An example of contextual anomaly.

Collective anomalies. If a collection of related data instances is anomalous with respect to the entire data set, it is defined as a *collective anomaly*. The individual instances might not be anomalies by themselves, but their occurrence together as a collection indicates an anomaly.

While point anomalies can occur in any data set, collective anomalies can

occur only in data sets in which instances are related.

A common example can be found in the medical field with electrocardiograms (ECGs - Figure 2.3), when the same value existing for an abnormally long time could indicate a health problem for the patient.

Figure 2.3: A collective anomaly in an ECG, marked in red.

2.3 Nature of input data

Anomaly detection methods are specific to the type of data. For instance, algorithms used to detect anomalies in images are different to the approaches used on data streams.

Input is generally a collection of data *instances*, also referred as *record*, *point*, *event*, *sample*, or *observation* [36]. Each data instance can be described using a set of *attributes* or *features*. The attributes can be of different types such as *binary*, *categorical* or *continuous*. Each data instance might consist of only one attribute (*univariate*) or multiple attributes (*multivariate*). In the case of multivariate data instances, all attributes might be of same type or might be a mixture of different data types.

Input data can also be categorised based on the relationship present among data instances [36]. Most of the existing anomaly detection techniques deal with point data, in which no relationship is assumed among the data instances.

In general, data instances can be related to each other. Some examples are *sequence data*, *spatial data*, and *graph data*.

In sequence data, the instances are linearly ordered, e.g., time series data, genome sequences, protein sequences. In spatial data, each data instance is related to its

neighbouring instances, e.g., vehicular traffic data, ecological data. In graph data, instances are represented as vertices in a graph and are connected to other vertices with edges.

As anticipated, the focus of this thesis is on time series data. Time series analysis can be classified into univariate and multivariate, based on the number of variables available for observation.

The *univariate* time series consists of a single scalar observation recorded sequentially over a time period. This may be a current trading price for a stock or share, or the electrical signal from a single trace in an electroencephalogram (EEG). The *multivariate* time series, instead, consists of more than one time-dependent variable, and each depends not only on its past values but also has some dependency on other variables. This may allow the anomaly detection method to build a more accurate model of the hidden processes behind the data it receives by utilising the additional contextual information.

An example of multivariate time series is proposed in Figure 2.4, taken from [37]. Here, the price of crude oil heavily influences the price of gasoline, but has a smaller influence on the price of lumber. Thus, given the realization that gasoline is produced from crude oil and lumber is not, we can use the price of crude oil to predict the price of gasoline.

Figure 2.4: Example of multivariate time series. Units are omitted and scales are normalised for simplicity.

Anomaly detection over univariate streams relies upon the comparison of the current observation against the local or global history of the time series being analysed. This is contrasted with multivariate streams, where not only is the history of the stream important to the detection task, but also the relationship between each of the measurements that combine to form the observation at a given time-step.

2.4 Output

An important aspect of any anomaly detection technique is the manner in which the results are reported. Typically, the output is of one of two types, *scores* or *labels*.

Scoring techniques assign an anomaly score to each data instance depending on the degree to which it is considered anomalous. This allows domain experts to select a specific threshold to choose the most relevant anomalies to analyse. Instead, techniques that directly assign a label (normal or anomalous) to an instance do not allow for such a choice, though it can still be controlled indirectly through parameter choices.

2.5 Data labels

As mentioned, the label associated with a data instance denotes if it is *normal* or *anomalous*.

Obtaining labelled data that is accurate as well as representative of all types of behaviour is often very difficult and expensive. Labelling is usually done manually by a human expert, so it requires a substantial effort to be obtained.

Typically, getting a labelled set of anomalous data instances that covers all possible types of anomalous behaviour is more difficult than getting labels for normal behaviour. Moreover, the anomalous behaviour is often dynamic in nature, e.g., new types of anomalies might arise for which there is no labelled training data. In certain cases, such as air traffic safety, anomalous instances would translate to catastrophic events, and hence will be very rare.

Based on the extent to which the labels are available, anomaly detection techniques can operate in one of the following three ways.

Supervised anomaly detection. Techniques trained in supervised mode assume the presence of a training data set which has labelled instances for both the normal and the anomaly class. A typical approach in such a case is to build a predictive model and, for an unseen data instance, compare it against the model to determine which class it belongs to. However, the number of anomalous instances is much smaller compared to the number of normal ones in the training data. Issues that arise due to imbalanced class distributions have been addressed in machine learning literature [38, 39].

Due to the difficulties stated above in obtaining labelled data, this category of techniques will not be addressed in this thesis.

Semi-supervised anomaly detection. Techniques that operate in a semi-supervised mode assume that the training data has labelled instances for only the normal class. Since they do not require labels for the anomaly class, they are more widely applicable than supervised techniques. The usual approach is to build a model for the expected normal behaviour and use it to identify anomalies in the test data.

Although a few semi-supervised anomaly detection techniques assume availability of only the anomaly instances for training [40, 41], they are not commonly used, mainly because of the difficulties in obtaining a training data set which covers every possible anomalous behaviour that could occur. This is the type of technique used in this thesis.

Unsupervised anomaly detection. Techniques that learn in an unsupervised manner do not require any labelled training data, making them the most widely applicable. These methods learn to inherit characteristics from the normal instances and the anomalous ones in an autonomous way, as well as the boundary between them. Unfortunately, this flexibility comes at the cost of robustness because unsupervised techniques are very sensitive to noise and data corruption, and are often less accurate than supervised or semi-supervised algorithms.

Many semi-supervised techniques can be adapted to operate in an unsupervised mode by using a sample of the unlabelled data set as training data. Such adaptation assumes that the test data contains very few anomalies and that the model learnt during training is robust to these few anomalies [33].

2.6 Challenges

The main problems and tasks anomaly detection focuses on refer to minority, unpredictable and rare events, leading to some unique problem complexities to detection methods. *Pang et al.* [42] and *Cook et al.* [34] identified the following challenges:

Unknownness. Anomalies are associated in many instances with unknown abrupt behaviours, data structures, and distributions. They remain unknown until they actually occur, such as network intrusions or malfunction of a sensor.

Heterogeneous anomaly classes. For definition, anomalies are irregular, and thus, one class of anomalies may show completely different behaviour and characteristics from another class of anomalies. For example, in video

surveillance, the abnormal events of robbery, traffic accidents and burglary are visually highly different.

Rarity. Anomalies are typically rare data instances and for this reason, it is difficult to collect a large amount of labelled abnormal instances, leading to an imbalanced data set. Since anomalies are highly rare and heterogeneous, it is difficult to identify all of them. Many normal instances are wrongly reported as anomalies while true yet sophisticated anomalies are missed. The class imbalance is also due to the fact that misclassification of anomalies is normally much more costly than that of normal instances.

Most of the time it is impossible to collect a full labelled data set, thus we must proceed in a semi-supervised or unsupervised way, which especially often incur in a high number of false positives [43, 44].

High-dimensional data. Anomalies often show clear abnormal characteristics in a low-dimensional space, yet become hidden and unnoticeable in a high-dimensional space. This has been a long-standing problem [45], usually approached with dimensionality reduction through subspace-based [46, 47, 48] or feature selection-based methods [49, 50].

Noise-resilient anomaly detection. Many semi-supervised algorithms assume the labelled training data is clean, which can be vulnerable to noisy instances that are mistakenly labelled as an opposite class label.

In such cases, an option is to use unsupervised methods instead, but this fails to utilize the labelled data. The main challenge is that the amount of noise can differ significantly from data sets and applications, and noisy instances may be irregularly distributed in the data space.

2.7 Applications

The importance of anomaly detection is due to the fact that anomalies in data translate to significant and often critical actionable information in a wide variety of application domains, such as:

Fraud detection. It refers to the detection of criminal activities occurring in organisations such as e-commerce, banks, insurance agencies, law firms, etc. The fraud occurs when a user consumes the resources provided by the organisation in an unauthorised way. A good fraud detection system should be able to identify fraudulent transactions accurately and should make

the detection possible in real-time, to prevent economic losses. The typical approach is to maintain a usage profile for each user and monitor it to detect any deviations [51].

Healthcare and Industrial domains. It tries to detect abnormal patient conditions, instrumentation errors or recording errors. Since this is a very critical problem, anomaly detection requires a high degree of accuracy. The data might also have a temporal as well as spatial aspect to it.

Similarly, in industrial systems like wind turbines, power plants, and storage devices that are exposed to large amounts of stress daily, it is critical to detect any damages as quickly as possible to prevent further escalation and losses.

In both cases, the most challenging aspect of the anomaly detection problem in this domain is the cost of classifying an anomaly as normal can be very high.

Image processing. Anomaly detection techniques dealing with images are either interested in any changes in an image over time (motion detection) or in regions which appear abnormal on the static image. This domain includes satellite imagery [52], digit recognition [53], and video surveillance [54].

2.8 Anomaly detection in WDS

Water is a resource for everybody, but in order to be drunk by the customers, it has to be captured, purified, stored, pumped, and distributed through the transmission and distribution networks up to their taps. The used water should be collected after use and sent to the water treatment plants for treatment in order to convey it to the natural environment cleaned via the Integrated Water Supply Service.

A water supply network or water supply system is a system of engineered hydrologic and hydraulic components that provides water supply (Figure 2.5).

Figure 2.5: Sketch of a typical Water Supply System.[55]

A WSS typically includes the following:

- A drainage basin.
- A raw water collection point (above or below ground) where the water accumulates, such as a lake, a river, or groundwater from an underground aquifer. Raw water may be transferred using uncovered ground-level aqueducts, covered tunnels, or underground water pipes to water purification facilities.
- Water purification facilities. Treated water is transferred using water pipes (usually underground).
- Water storage facilities such as reservoirs, water tanks, or water towers. Smaller water systems may store the water in cisterns or pressure vessels.
- Additional water-pressurizing components such as pumping stations may need to be situated at the outlet of underground or aboveground reservoirs or cisterns (if gravity flow is impractical).
- A pipe network for distribution of water to consumers (which may be private houses or industrial, commercial, or institutional establishments) and other usage points (such as fire hydrants).

Water has to be managed according to the principles of efficiency, effectiveness, and economy, according to national rules and Community environmental legislation. The management of the water supply is a matter of infrastructure: in Italy, the property of the assets is owned by the Italian Country, provinces and municipalities. The water utilities manage the WSS [2]. The importance of the integrated water supply service was stated for the first time in the Italian Law 336/1994 (also known as Galli Law) and the principles were embedded afterwards in the D. Lgs. 152/2006 about the Italian Environmental Regulation.

The regulation of water services is carried out in Italy on a national scale by the ARERA, the Italian Regulatory Authority for Energy, Networks and Environment, and at local level by the EGA (Ente Governo d'Ambito). ARERA is a single mission authority, i.e., an authority that has as main objective to establish the rules that allow the water utilities to reach the social and environmental goals of the service that are identified by the EGA at the most economically efficient conditions [1].

The water crises of the 2010s, partly attributable to climate change, together with the difficulties highlighted by the sector in promoting a stable improvement in its infrastructural performance, led the ARERA Authority to define a specific regulation for technical quality of the integrated water service (RQTI), which entered into force in 2018. On the basis of the data available at the time (2016) and certain evidence relating to particularly critical contexts, specific improvement objectives were set for certain technical macro-areas defined by the Authority, requiring operators to accurately identify the measures adopted in different contexts to address critical issues in a timely manner [10].

The novel system, known as “Technical quality of the integrated water service (RQTI)” [56], pursues the achievement of minimum service levels through:

- the provision of automatic compensation to end users who experience a disruption in water supply, measured on the basis of three indicators associated with specific standards
- the introduction of a bonus-penalty mechanism in the event of failure to achieve the objectives set for some indicators associated with general quality standards, called *macroindicators*.

MACRO-INDICATORS DEFINED BY THE RQTI	
M1	Containment of water losses in aqueduct networks and systems
M2	Maintenance of the continuity of the drinking water service, based on the measurement of the frequency of service interruptions
M3	Adequacy of the quality of the water supplied
M4	Minimisation of the environmental impact of the conveyance of waste water, measured on the basis of the degree of adequacy of the sewage system
M5	Minimisation of the environmental impact associated with the disposal of sludge deriving from the purification of waste water
M6	Minimisation of the environmental impact associated with the disposal of waste water from purification treatments

Figure 2.6: Macro-Indicators defined by the RQTI for the Water Supply Systems.

The performance improvement goals are based on key performance indicators that are used to measure the performances of water utilities (operators) (Figure 2.6). Those related to water supply systems are:

1. *M1*: water leakages indicator;
2. *M2*: water supply service interruption indicator;
3. *M3*: supplied water quality indicator.

The indicator *M1* summarizes the conservation of water resource and is calculated according to the following sub-indicators:

M1a – **linear water leakages**. They are defined as the ratio between the volume of total water losses and the total length of the water supply network for the considered year (mc/km/gg). For each a year, the indicator *M1a* is calculated according to the following formula:

$$M1a^a = \frac{WL_{TOT}^a}{365 \cdot Lp^a}$$

where:

- $WL_{TOT}^a = \sum W_{IN}^a - \sum W_{OUT}^a$ is the total water volume lost in year *a*, defined as the difference between the sum of the input volumes and the sum of the output water volumes;
- Lp^a is the total length of both water mains and distribution pipes (customer connections are not included), managed on December 31st of year *a*;

M1b – percentage water leakages. They are defined as the ratio of total real losses and the total volume entering the WSS in the considered year a (%):

$$M1b^a = \frac{WL_{TOT}^a}{\sum W_{IN}^a}.$$

Once the $M1a$ e $M1b$ indicators are calculated it is possible to establish the class of performance for the considered year according to the following picture (Figure 2.7).

		Perdite idriche lineari (mc/km/gg)				
		M1a <15	15 ≤ M1a <25	25 ≤ M1a <40	40 ≤ M1a <60	M1a ≥60
Perdite idriche percentuali	M1b <25%	A				
	25% ≤ M1b <35%		B			
	35% ≤ M1b <45%			C		
	45% ≤ M1b <55%				D	
	M1b ≥55%					E

Figure 2.7: Performance class of the water supply network according to water leakages.

Afterwards, the goals in terms of maintenance/improvement of $M1a$ indicator can be established according to the following Figure 2.8.

ID	Indicatore	Categoria tariffaria	ID Classe	Obiettivi
M1	M1a - Perdite idriche lineari [mc/km/gg] M1b – Perdite idriche percentuali [%]	RES	A	Mantenimento
			B	-2% di M1a annuo
			C	-4% di M1a annuo
			D	-5% di M1a annuo
			E	-6% di M1a annuo

Figure 2.8: Goals to be achieved according to the performance class of the water supply system.

The calculation of $M1$ requires a monitoring system for water distribution networks to be in place in order to measure the quantity of water supplied and consumed by the customers.

The annual reports by ARERA shed light on the actual condition of the water supply systems in Italy that are, in many cases, outdated and not appropriate to offer a complete and advanced service, with a division between the North and South parts of the country. Nevertheless, from the first application of the

technical quality regulation, nationally the figure for average value of percentage water losses has improved (at 41.2% in 2021 compared to 43.7% in 2016), and there has also been a reduction in the values of the indicators referring to service interruptions of 26% and a decrease of non-potability ordinances [10].

In conclusion, though the situation is improving, still a lot of work is needed in order to ensure in Italy a sustainable water use and management of water leakages in particular. The problem of water losses is very complex and requires the implementation of continuous actions: on one hand most of water losses are not visible, on the other hand a WSS with no water leakages at all is not economically nor technically feasible. The International Water Association (IWA) water loss task force and American Water Works Association (AWWA) water loss control committee suggest an approach that integrates four different methods for controlling water losses sketched in Figure 2.9), namely

- Active leakage control
- Pressure management
- Speed and quality of repairs
- Asset management

Figure 2.9: The four primary methods of controlling water losses (IWA water loss task force and AWWA Water loss control committee)

The reduction of excess pressure via the pressure management is widely recognized as being able to reduce leak flow rates and the frequency of bursts. Active Leakage Control (ALC) is the process of pro-actively looking for unreported leaks and bursts (in order to reduce their run time) and identifying those water losses outflows that are visible on the ground surface.

ALC consists of two separate stages:

1. the leak monitoring and localization, whose aim is the identification of the area of the network in which leakage is occurring in order to prioritise the field surveys;
2. the leak location and pinpointing phase, which is usually implemented once the leak has been localised, and is performed using various techniques (acoustic and non-acoustic).

The leak monitoring and localization is usually implemented by partitioning the network, i.e., dividing the WDS into District Metered Areas (DMAs) by shutting valves and installing flow rate and pressure meters with telemetry data loggers. The partitioning allows the water utility operators to continuously monitor the inflows and outflows, hence the district consumption when performing the water balance for each DMA. Variations of the water balance are insights of a potential water leakage, that thanks to the recorded time series can be quantified at DMA scale. The DMA-based strategy can be implemented temporarily and permanently. Hybrid solutions that use both mobile and permanent meters and valve closures can also be adopted. Within a DMA, the leak can be further localised by shutting valves inside the district to isolate sections of the mains or moving temporarily the DMA boundary changing the location of the meters or the valves' closure (*step testing*). Finally, the leakage can be pinpointed in the field using acoustic methodologies.

By performing data analysis on these water consumption flow data, it is possible not only to manage water loss, but also to detect atypical consumption behaviour, and control the operation of pumps and valves. Therefore, the existence of a reliable and complete consumption data history is fundamental to the operational management of these systems.

It is worth noting that ALC as well as the ARERA's RQTI regulation shall be based on validated time series extracted from sensors placed throughout the WDN: in particular, the estimate of $M1$ macro-indicator requires validated data that cover a whole solar year.

In fact, the lack of validated data may cause:

- Impossibility of performing the water balance (without the time series of one sensor, the calculation cannot be computed), the basic information for water supply macro-indicator M1.
- Impossibility of running robust numerical simulations of the hydraulic functioning of the network, often required in real-time.
- Impossibility of forecasting the future water demand, usually based on available historical data.

Flow data are often faulty (e.g., missing, duplicate, or out of range values), and extracting useful information from it can be a difficult task. A relevant issue regarding water consumption time series is the occurrence of missing data, which usually results from problems with the equipment's power supply, with the communication system between the sensors and data loggers, or with the exiting data storage and processing.

Therefore, in order to estimate useful statistics, such as the instantaneous, daily, or monthly water consumption value, it is necessary to have complete and accurate data. Besides the importance for billing and customers management, complete and accurate flow data are crucial to improve water loss (e.g., night flow analysis) and demand management (e.g., large consumers consumption analysis). It is worth noting that flow data may present, for instance, unusually high values during a low flow period, which could indicate the occurrence of pipe bursts. Events such as this are considered anomalous because they are not periodic and are not representative of typical water consumption patterns.

Performing leakage control, as well as detecting changes in customer water demand or manoeuvring in the network, can be summarised as physical anomaly detection. To perform this task, the time series of flow rate and pressure need to be analysed and passed through an anomaly detection model.

Chapter 3

Deep anomaly detection models

Given a data set $\mathcal{X} = x_1, x_2, \dots, x_N$, *deep anomaly detection* aims at learning an anomaly score function $\tau(\cdot) : \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, or *anomaly index*, in a way that anomalies can be easily differentiated from the normal data instances. Larger τ outputs indicate greater degree of being anomalous.

A possible way to learn this anomaly index is by dividing the anomaly detection process into two separate steps. First, a prediction phase. Here, a model trained on "normal" data (i.e. without anomalies) is used to perform a prediction on the time series, and all errors are recorded and saved. As a second step, the distribution of these errors is drawn, and the anomaly score function τ is learned from it. The more an error performed by the model is an outlier in the learned error distribution, the higher the value of τ will be. The reasoning behind it being that the point for which the model committed an abnormally large prediction error is a point which does not follow the trend that the model learned, therefore has a good chance at being an anomaly.

In this chapter, five architectures are introduced, along with techniques to tune their hyperparameters. Moreover, a selection of existing error metrics is analysed, and a new one is proposed. These are then used at a later moment to compare the models and to select the best-performing one in order to conduct anomaly detection.

3.1 Deep learning architectures

Deep neural networks (DNNs) exploit complex compositions of linear and non-linear functions that can be represented by a computational graph to learn expressive representations. Two basic building blocks of deep learning are activation functions and layers. *Activation functions*, which can be linear or non-linear, determine the output of neurons given some inputs. Some popular activation functions include, with their variants:

Linear. The function is linear, therefore its output will not be confined between any range. The function does not modify the weighted sum of the input, simply returning the value it was given. It does not help with the complexity or various parameters of usual data that is fed to the neural networks. If a linear activation function is used, all layers of the neural network will collapse into one.

Sigmoid. The sigmoid function, given by

$$f(x) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-x}},$$

is especially used for models where the output is a probability, as it exists between 0 and 1. The function is differentiable and provides a smooth gradient, preventing jumps in output values.

Tanh. The hyperbolic tangent function is very similar to the sigmoid activation function, and even has the same S-shape, with the difference in output range $(-1, 1)$. The advantage is that the negative inputs will be mapped strongly negative and the zero inputs will be mapped near zero in the tanh graph. For this reason, it is often used in hidden layers of a neural network, so that its mean will be 0, or very close to it. It helps in centring the data and makes learning for the next layer much easier. Mathematically, it can be represented as

$$f(x) = \frac{e^x - e^{-x}}{e^x + e^{-x}}$$

ReLU. Short for Rectified Linear Unit [57], it computes the function

$$f(x) = \max(0, x).$$

This activation function does not activate all the neurons at the same time, but only if the output of the linear transformation is greater than 0. This

way, it is more computationally efficient when compared to the sigmoid and tanh functions. Moreover, ReLU accelerates the convergence of gradient descent towards the global minimum of the loss function due to its linear, non-saturating property. For these reasons, it is one of the most popular activation functions at the moment.

A *layer* in a neural network refers to a set of neurons stacked in some form. These can be used to build different popular neural networks, such as Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs), Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) and their many variants.

In the following subsections, five architectures are analysed. These, with their optimal hyperparameters, were compared to find the best performing model in terms of predictive error minimisation.

3.1.1 RNNs

Recurrent neural networks or RNN [58] are a family of artificial neural networks for processing sequential data. Their connections between nodes can create a cycle, allowing output from some nodes to affect subsequent input to the same nodes. RNNs have a memory that stores all information about the calculations. It employs the same settings for each input since it produces the same outcome by performing the same task on all inputs or hidden layers.

Following the notation in Figure 3.1. For each time-step t , the activation a_t and the output \hat{y}_t are expressed as follows:

$$a_t = g_1(W_{aa} a_{t-1} + W_{ax} x_t + b_a) \quad \text{and} \quad \hat{y}_t = g_2(W_{ya} a_t + b_y)$$

where x_t is the input, $W_{aa}, W_{ax}, W_{ya}, b_a, b_y$ are weight matrices for the input, recurrent connections, and the output, respectively that are shared temporally, and g_1, g_2 are activation functions.

Figure 3.1: Standard RNN architecture. Source: *stanford.edu*

Figure 3.2: Architecture of a typical RNN block. Source: *stanford.edu*

For training such networks, Back Propagation Through Time (BPTT) is used, a generalisation of back-propagation. In this family of gradient-based methods, during each iteration of training each of the neural network's weights receives an update proportional to the partial derivative of the error function with respect to the current weight [59].

The discrepancy between the output \hat{y}_t and the desired target y_t is evaluated by said error function across all T time-steps as

$$L(x, y, W) = \sum_{t=1}^T l_t(y_t, \hat{y}_t),$$

which is then minimised through forward and backward passes.

These gradients are backpropagated through layers and through time. Hence at each time-step all the previous contributions are summed up, until the current one.

Two common problems that occur during the backpropagation in RNNs are the exploding and vanishing gradients. More explicitly, they happen because of recursive derivative needed at each step

$$\prod_{j=k}^t \frac{\partial a_{j+1}}{\partial a_j} = \frac{\partial a_{t+1}}{\partial a_k}.$$

When $\|\frac{\partial a_{t+1}}{\partial a_k}\|_2 > 1$, the term goes to infinity exponentially fast, making the process unstable. This is called *exploding gradient* and it happens when large error gradients accumulate and result in very large updates to neural network model weights during training. There are methods to fix exploding gradients,

such as gradient clipping and weight regularisation.

On the other hand, when $\|\frac{\partial a_{t+1}}{\partial a_k}\|_2 < 1$, the term goes to 0 exponentially fast, effectively preventing the weight from changing its value and making it difficult to learn some long period dependencies. In the worst case, this *vanishing gradient* may completely stop the neural network from further training [59].

To overcome this shortcoming when learning long-term dependencies, the *Long Short-Term Memory* (LSTM) network [60] was introduced. This is the first of the five architectures considered in this thesis.

The learning ability of LSTM impacted several fields from both a practical and theoretical perspective, so that it became a state-of-the-art model used by Google, Amazon, and Meta, among others [61].

Figure 3.3: Architecture of a typical LSTM block, adapted from [61].

A vanilla LSTM unit (Figure 3.3) is composed of a cell c_t , an input gate, an output gate and a forget gate, along with the input signal x_t , the output y_t , and the activation functions. This forget gate was not initially a part of the LSTM network, but was proposed by *Gers et al.* [62] to allow the network to reset its state. The cell remembers values over arbitrary time intervals and the three gates regulate the flow of information associated with the cell. Going more in detail with this forward pass:

Block input. This step updates the block input component, which combines the current output x_t and the output of the previous unit y_{t-1} . This can be done as depicted below:

$$z_t = g(W_z x_t + R_z y_{t-1} + b_z)$$

where W_z and R_z are the weights associated with x_t and y_{t-1} , respectively,

while b_z stands for the bias weight vector.

Input gate. In this step, the input gate is updated by combining the current input x_t , the output of that unit y_{t-1} and the cell value c_{t-1} in the last iteration. The following equation shows this procedure:

$$i_t = \sigma(W_i x_t + R_i y_{t-1} + p_i \odot c_{t-1} + b_i)$$

where \odot denotes point-wise multiplication of two vectors, W_i , R_i and p_i are the weights associated with x_t , y_{t-1} and c_{t-1} , respectively, while b_i represents for the bias vector associated with this component.

Forget gate. In this step, the LSTM unit determines which information should be removed from its previous cell states c_{t-1} . Therefore, the activation values f_t of the forget gates at time-step t are calculated based on the current input x_t , the outputs y_{t-1} and the state c_{t-1} of the memory cells at the previous time.step $t1$, the peephole connections, and the bias terms b_f of the forget gates. This can be done as follows:

$$f_t = \sigma(W_f x_t + R_f y_{t-1} + p_f \odot c_{t-1} + b_f)$$

where W_f , R_f and p_f are the weights associated with x_t , y_{t-1} and c_{t-1} , respectively, while b_f denotes for the bias weight vector.

Cell. This step computes the cell value, which combines the block input z_t , the input gate i_t and the forget gate f_t values, with the previous cell values. This can be done as depicted below:

$$c_t = z_t \odot i_t + c_{t-1} \odot f_t.$$

Output gate. This step calculates the output gate, which combines the current input x_t , the output of the previous unit y_{t-1} and the cell value c_{t-1} in the last iteration. The following equation shows this procedure:

$$o_t = \sigma(W_o x_t + R_o y_{t-1} + p_o \odot c_{t-1} + b_o)$$

where W_o , R_o and p_o are the weights associated with x_t , y_{t-1} and c_{t-1} , respectively, while b_o denotes for the bias weight vector.

The update gate and the reset gate follow the equations depicted below, respectively:

$$z_t = \sigma(W_z x_t + R_z y_{t-1} + b_z)$$

$$r_t = \sigma(W_r x_t + R_r y_{t-1} + b_r)$$

where W_z, W_r, R_z and R_r are the weights associated with x_t and y_{t-1} , respectively, while b_z and b_r denote for the bias weight vector.

Next, the reset gate is updated, leading to the *candidate hidden state* \tilde{h}_t :

$$\tilde{h}_t = \tanh(W_h x_t + R_h (r_t \odot y_{t-1}) + b_h)$$

where W_h and R_h are the weights associated with x_t and y_{t-1} , respectively, b_h denotes for the bias weight vector and \odot indicates the point-wise multiplication of two vectors. The result is a *candidate*, since the action of the update gate still needs to be incorporated.

3.1.2 Variations of CNNs

A *Convolutional Neural Network* (CNN) is a class of Artificial Neural Network, most commonly applied to analyse visual imagery.

CNN is a construct that is typically composed of three types of layers (or building blocks): convolution, pooling, and fully connected layers. The first two, convolution and pooling layers, perform feature extraction, whereas the third, a fully connected layer, maps the extracted features into final output [65]. A typical architecture consists of repetitions of a stack of several convolution layers and a pooling layer, followed by one or more fully connected layers, as illustrated in Figure 3.5.

The convolutional layer typically consists of a combination of linear and non-

Figure 3.5: Basic architecture of CNN. Source: *Gu et al.* [66].

linear operations, i.e., convolution operations and an activation function.

A convolution is a specialised of linear operation used for feature extraction, where a *kernel*, a two-dimensional array of weights, is applied across the input tensor. A dot product between each element of the kernel and the input tensor is calculated at each location of the tensor and summed to obtain the output value in the corresponding position of the two-dimensional output tensor, called a *feature map*. This procedure is repeated applying multiple kernels to form an arbitrary number of feature maps, which represent different characteristics of the input tensors; different kernels can, thus, be considered as different feature extractors [65]. Two key hyperparameters that define the convolution operation are size and number of kernels. The former is to be set depending on the application, while the latter is arbitrary, and determines the depth of output feature maps.

The convolution operation described above does not allow the centre of each kernel to overlap the outermost element of the input tensor, and reduces the height and width of the output feature map compared to the input tensor. Padding, typically Zero Padding, is a technique to address this issue, where rows and columns of zeros are added on each side of the input tensor, so as to fit the centre of a kernel on the outermost element and keep the same dimension through the convolution operation. Without zero padding, each successive feature map would get smaller after the convolution operation.

Training a CNN model with regard to the convolution layer means to identify the kernels that work best for a task based on a given data set. Kernels are the only parameters automatically learned during the training process in the convolution layer. On the other hand, the size of the kernels, number of kernels, padding, and stride are hyperparameters that need tuned to obtain the best performance possible.

The outputs of the convolution are then passed through a non-linear activation function. Although smooth non-linear functions, such as sigmoid or hyperbolic tangent (\tanh), were used previously because of their tie to biological neuron behaviour, now the most common non-linear activation function is the Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU).

A pooling layer provides a downsampling operation which reduces the dimensionality of the feature maps in order to introduce a translation invariance to small shifts and distortions, and decrease the number of subsequent learnable parameters. This decreases the computational power required to process the data, while controlling overfitting as well.

The most popular form of pooling operation is Max Pooling, which extracts

patches from the input feature maps, outputs the maximum value in each patch, and discards all the other values. This pooling also performs as a noise suppressor by discarding the noisy activations altogether.

The output feature maps of the final convolution or pooling layer is typically flattened, i.e., transformed into a one-dimensional array of numbers (or vector), and connected to one or more fully connected layers, also known as dense layers, in which every input is connected to every output by a learnable weight. Each fully connected layer is followed by a non-linear function, such as ReLU, as described earlier in this section.

As mentioned, CNNs' convolutions are popularly known to work on spatial or 2D data. However, these convolutions exist also for one-dimensional data, allowing CNNs to be used with more general data types including texts and time series.

Generally, CNNs are computationally cheaper than RNNs, since they learn in batches and can use parallelisation [67]. However, RNNs are built to efficiently capture sequence pattern information.

The third architecture considered in this work combines the advantages of CNN, that can extract effective features and filter out the noise from the input data, and the capacity of LSTM for prediction with both short and long temporal dependencies [68]. The first layer of a CNN-LSTM architecture, as depicted in Figure 3.6, consists of CNN, which extracts features to pass to the next layer, the LSTM, which stores time information about important characteristics extracted through the previous layer.

Figure 3.6: Architecture of CNN-LSTM. Source: *Livieris et al.* [69].

The last CNN-based architecture a *Temporal Convolutional Network* (TCN), introduced in 2018 by *Bai et al.* [70]. The authors claim this family of architectures to exhibit "substantially longer memory", and thus be more suitable where a long history is required. They also claim it to be not only more accurate than canonical RNNs such as LSTMs and GRUs, but also to be "simpler and clearer".

The TCN is based upon the facts that the network produces an output of the same length as the input, and that there can be no leakage from the future into the past. To accomplish this, the TCN uses a 1D full-convolutional network with Zero Padding and *dilated causal convolutions*, convolutions where an output at time t is convolved only with elements from time t and earlier in the previous layer, and that allow an exponentially large receptive field.

The residual block for our baseline TCN is shown in Figure 3.7(b). Within a residual block, the TCN has two layers of dilated causal convolution and non-linearity brought in by a Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU). For normalisation, a weight normalisation is applied to the convolutional filters and for regularisation, a spatial dropout was added after each dilated convolution: at each training step, a whole channel is zeroed out. To account for discrepant input-output widths, an additional 1×1 convolution is added, to ensure that the element-wise addition \oplus receives tensors of the same shape.

The authors praise their family of architectures to have stable gradients, unlike RNNs, thus avoiding issues of exploding or vanishing gradients, and to require low memory for training, thanks to the filters being shared across a layer.

Figure 3.7: Architectural elements in a TCN. Source: *Bai et al.*

(a) A dilated causal convolution with dilation factors $d = 1, 2, 4$ and filter size $k = 3$. The receptive field is able to cover all values from the input sequence.

(b) TCN residual block. An 1×1 convolution is added when residual input and output have different dimensions. [70].

3.1.3 Transformer

The *Transformer* neural network was first proposed in a 2017 paper "*Attention is all you need*" by *Vaswani et al.* [71] and has been designed to deal with sequences or in general data that can be divided into tokens whose order is meaningful. As such, transformers have been initially applied in the field of Natural Language Processing (NLP) before extending their use to other contexts, such as computer vision.

Its aim is to solve all problems related to RNNs, from slowness in training to the vanishing gradient problem. While the latter is solved by architectures such as LSTM, the former continues to present as an issue.

The authors take on solving the vanishing gradient problem is *attention*, first introduced in 2015 [72]. It highly improves the quality of the output as it allows the model to focus on the relevant part of the input sequence as necessary. Transformers are seeing high consideration thanks to the many advantages brought by the attention mechanism: compared to RNNs, the input sequence can be passed in a parallel manner, and the speed of training can also be increased. Moreover, the limited receptive field of CNNs and vanishing gradient issues of standard RNNs hinder the ability to model long-range dependencies, while it has been found [71] that attention can model dependencies with unprecedented effectiveness in even longer sequences.

The resulting encoder-decoder architecture based on attention layers was termed as the Transformer. Its architecture, represented in Figure 3.8, is comprised of two sub-models. The *Encoder* (left side of the Figure), responsible for stepping through the input time-steps and encoding the entire sequence into a fixed length vector called a *context vector*. It consists of a variable number of stacked layers, where each consists of

- a Multihead Self-Attention Module (MSA), that produces a new set of encodings by applying the self-attention mechanism on each input encoding. Self-attention allows the inputs to interact with each other and find out who they should pay more attention to. The outputs are aggregates of these interactions and attention scores.
- a Multilayer Perceptron (MLP) head, which is a feed-forward neural network that further embeds each encoding.

Figure 3.8: The Transformer - model architecture. Source: *Vaswani et al.* [71].

The second part is the *Decoder* (right side of the Figure), responsible for stepping through the output time-steps while reading the context vector. Its structure is similar to the one of the Encoder since each block consists of a self-attention layer, an MLP head, and an extra attention layer that processes the encodings coming from the Encoder in order to perform meaningful sequence transduction from input encodings to output encodings. In the architecture proposed in [71], an additional final block which consists of a fully connected layer and a softmax layer is added in order to produce the probability distribution over the vocabulary for every output token, useful when applying the network to NLP tasks.

3.2 Error evaluation

To evaluate the error committed by a model, many different metrics have been considered.

The most desirable properties were:

A. Scale invariance. The error should be the same if both the true value and predicted value are multiplied by a common factor.

E.g. $err(x = 0.1, y = 0.5) = err(x = 1, y = 5)$, where x is the true value and y is the predicted one.

This is crucial in order to have linearity in the values and be able to set a threshold to record an anomaly. If there wasn't linearity and an upper or lower limit existed, to which the function would tend to, too many values were to be similar in an interval near said limit. If the threshold were to be put in this interval, the possible density of values around it may cause some problems.

B. Symmetry. A metric should penalise positive and negative errors equally.

E.g. $err(x = 0.5, y = 0.1) = err(x = 0.5, y = 0.9)$.

C. Stability at all points. The metric should be defined at every point.

This is notably not true for every metric which is calculated as a ratio of two values.

D. Informativeness. The metric should provide useful, direct information.

3.2.1 Metrics

Following, a review of the metrics that were considered to compute the final results and choose the best performing model.

To maintain significant values for metrics undefined in some points, every infinite value was replaced with **None**.

AE. The Absolute Error (AE) is the difference between the values predicted by the model and the true values. It is calculated as

$$AE = |y - x|.$$

This uses the same scale as the data being measured, which makes it unambiguous and intuitive to understand. Nevertheless, for the same reason it cannot be used to make comparisons between data sets using different scales. The properties it satisfies are B, C and D.

APE. If the AE is scaled by the true values, it becomes the Absolute Percentage Error:

$$APE = \frac{|y - x|}{|x|}.$$

The formula often includes multiplying the value by 100%, to express the number as percentage.

Intuitively, APE indicates how much error in predicting compared with the real value. It is easily understandable, being expressed as a percentage, and scale-independent, which makes it useful for comparison across data sets with different scales. However, it has numerous shortcomings.

APE is not defined when the actual value is 0, and takes extreme values when it gets very close to it. Moreover, it is asymmetric having a bias favouring estimates that are below the actual values [73]. That is, if the true value and the predicted one were to be inverted, the error value would change.

Reporting the example in the paper by *Armstrong et al.* [73]: when $x = 150$ and $y = 100$, the APE is 33.3%. However, when $x = 100$ and $y = 150$, the APE raises to 50%.

Given these considerations, the properties it satisfies are A, B and D.

s2APE. To avoid this asymmetry of the APE, the author of the paper [73] proposed the "adjusted APE", which could also take negative measures.

A few years later, another author [74] proposed almost the same measure but as an absolute value, calling it Symmetric APE (sAPE):

$$sAPE = \left| \frac{y - x}{(x + y)/2} \right|.$$

Now the denominator is the midpoint between true and predicted value, making it much less likely for it to be zero and for the metric to be undefined. This can be seen happening in Figure 3.9, where $x = -y$.

Although this modified APE is symmetric when x and y are interchanged, it faces the problem of asymmetry stated in the desirable properties: differently from APE, sAPE treats single errors above the actual value differently from those below it [75] (see Figure 3.9). Therefore, the sAPE satisfies no properties.

In an attempt of solving the asymmetry introduced by sAPE, a new metric has been introduced, called Symmetric Symmetric APE (s2APE). It is defined as

$$s2APE = \frac{|y - x|}{|x| + |y - x|}.$$

Now there is no direct dependency on the predicted value, which was causing the asymmetry.

For this metric to be undefined, i.e. the denominator to be 0, both the true value and the absolute error must be 0. Hence, for the latter, the predicted value is exactly the true one, so the error can be said to be 0.

Figure 3.9: Comparison between considered error metrics.

This indeed solves the problem, but introduces a logarithmic-like scaling, which goes against the request for scale invariance. This last metric can then be said to satisfy properties B, C, and arguably D.

3.3 Anomaly detection model definition

Once the predictive model has been trained and tested, the anomaly detection part of the work can begin. The metric of choice in this thesis is the APE, which was appreciated for its symmetry (of one kind) and scale invariance. By using its average produced in training on the test data set by the predictive model, $\mathbb{E}[APE]_{model}$, the anomaly index τ for each sensor on a given data set can be calculated as the in the following way:

$$\tau_i^{OG} = \begin{cases} APE(x_i, y_i) - \mathbb{E}[APE]_{model} & \text{if } > 0 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

where x_i is the true value of the data set and y_i is the predictive model's prediction of that value.

All negative values are clipped to 0, because if the prediction error of the objective data point is lower than the average error of the model, it means that its probability of being an anomaly is low enough to be considered irrelevant.

Instead, the greater the prediction error is from the average error of the model, the greater possibility that point has to be anomalous.

The anomaly threshold, over which a data point is considered anomalous, can be given by

$$\text{thres} = 3 \sigma[APE],$$

where σ is the standard deviation.

This is an arbitrary value which can be modified in order to set a personalised threshold. It was chosen because it is a standard reference value and, by applying it, 99.7% of data points do not exceed it. This parameter can be tuned to change the sensitivity to anomalies based on different use cases.

Lastly, to give more readability to the anomaly index, it was linearly scaled in order to make the interval $[0, \text{thres}]$ coincide with the interval $[0, 1]$. Points over the threshold assume values greater than 1. This was done using the following formula:

$$\text{thres} : 1 = \tau_i^{OG} : \tau_i.$$

In Figure 3.10 it is shown the distribution of the anomaly index values of the predictive model on flow rate sensors values. The plot has a logarithmic scale on y-axis. In red, all the bins over the threshold, and its value in the top-left corner. The blue bin, representing the data points underneath the threshold, almost reaches 1, indicating that most points are not considered anomalous.

Figure 3.10: Distribution of the sensor anomaly index on the flow rate sensors, with a logarithmic scale on the y-axis. In red, in the top-left corner, the value of the threshold, and in the same colour all the bins with values greater than it.

3.4 Training the models

Deep learning neural networks learn a mapping function from inputs to outputs. To develop a model, historical data from the domain is required, to use it as training data. This is comprised of observations with input elements that describe the conditions, and an output element that captures the result.

A neural network model uses these examples to learn how to map specific input variables to the output variable, and must do it in a way that works well for the training data set, but also on examples not seen by the model during training. This is achieved by updating the weights of the network in response to the errors the model makes on the training data set. Once small random weights are initialised, updates are made to continually reduce this error until either a good enough model is found or the learning process gets stuck and stops. However, the use of nonlinear activation functions in the neural network means that the optimisation problem to must solve in order to find model parameters is not convex. This leads to many good and many misleadingly good sets of parameters that may be discovered.

The process of training neural networks is the most challenging part of using the technique and is by far the most time consuming, both in terms of effort required to configure the process and computational complexity required to execute the process

Training a deep neural network model involves choosing a number of components and hyperparameters. An error function must be chosen, often called a *loss function*. This takes as input the output value of the model and the ground truth expected value. The output is a measure of how well the model did at predicting the outcome. A high loss means the model performed poorly, while a low value means it performed very well.

The Mean Squared Error (MSE) is perhaps the simplest and most common loss function. It is formally defined by the following equation:

$$MSE = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2$$

where N is the number of samples the test is done against. This value will never be negative since the error is always squared. The MSE is great for ensuring that the trained model has no outlier predictions with huge errors since it puts more weight on them due to the squaring part of the function. On the other hand, if a model makes a single very bad decision, the squaring part of the

function magnifies the error. However, in practical cases, these outliers are not very important, since the aim is more of a well-rounded model that performs well enough in the majority.

Once an error gradient has been estimated, it can be used to update network weights. There may be statistical noise in the training data set and in the estimate of the error gradient. Also, the fact that the model hyperparameters are updated separately means that it is hard to calculate exactly how much to change each parameter to best improve the model.

Instead, a small portion of the update to the weights is performed at each iteration. A hyperparameter called *learning rate*, to be tuned, controls how much to update model weights and, consequently, how fast a model learns on the training data set.

The learning rate is controlled through an *optimiser*. An optimiser is an algorithm used to minimise the loss function and to maximise the efficiency of production. While many types of optimisers exist, one of the most popular is the Adaptive Moment estimation (Adam) [76], an extension to stochastic gradient descent (SGD). While SGD maintains a single learning rate for all weight updates and does not change it during training, Adam adapts it for each parameter using past gradients. According to the creators, the method is "computationally efficient, has little memory requirement, is invariant to diagonal rescaling of gradients, and is well suited for problems that are large in terms of data and parameters".

The training process must be repeated many times until a good enough set of model parameters is discovered. The total number of iterations of the process is bounded by the number of complete passes through the training data set, after which the training process is finished. This is referred to as the number of training *epochs*.

All the considered architectures in Section 3.1 are *sliding window based* [77]. The input, in this thesis a time series, is converted to a vector by splitting it into a sequence of overlapping, ordered, fixed-size windows of length L . This way, the data set is restructured as inputs-output pairs, where the window of prior time-steps as input can be used to predict the value at the next time-step. A visual representation of the process is shown in Figure 3.11, with $L = 5$.

The number of time-steps ahead to be forecasted is important. Most commonly, and also in this work, only the next time-step is predicted, creating a *one step forecast*. Another option is to predict two or more future time-steps. The length L of the window controls how many neighbouring points are included in the

calculation of the prediction value. The larger the window width is, the more points are included. By selecting the proper size of a sliding window, the model efficiency can also be improved.

Figure 3.11: Sliding window method illustrated with an example sequence of numbers. Here, the window length is $L = 5$, with a one-step forecast.

3.5 Hyperparameter tuning

The aim of hyperparameter optimisation is to find the hyperparameters of a given machine learning algorithm that return the best performance as measured on a validation set.

Hyperparameter optimisation is represented in equation form as

$$x^* = \arg \min_{x \in X} f(x)$$

where $f(x)$ represents an objective score to minimise (or, in some cases, maximise), options of which are presented in section 3.2, evaluated on a validation set. x^* is the set of hyperparameters that yields the lowest value of the score, and x can take on any value in the domain X .

The most intuitive traditional approach to perform hyperparameter optimisation is Grid Search [78], which generates a Cartesian product of all possible combinations of hyperparameters and trains the model on each one of them. This is obviously the most straightforward hyperparameter tuning method and guarantees the detection of the best hyperparameters. However, one of its drawbacks is that it suffers severely when it comes to rapid convergence and dimensionality. If k parameters with n distinct values are tested, the complexity of Grid Search is expected to grow exponentially at a rate of $O(n^k)$ [79].

A solution to the complexity is found in Random Search [80]. This is a technique in which random combinations of the hyperparameters are used to find the best solution for the model under consideration. The number of evaluations in Random Search must be set in the beginning, before the hyperparameter

optimisation process starts, and hence, the complexity of Random Search running n evaluations is $O(n)$ [81]. A significant drawback of the Random Search algorithm is that it does not use information from prior trials to select the next set and it also does not use a strategy to predict the next trial.

A more interesting approach to fine-tune hyperparameters through automated model tuning is the Bayesian optimisation (BO) algorithm. This is the approach used in this thesis.

Bayesian optimisation [82] is an *informed* search algorithm, which means that each iteration of this algorithm learns from the previous one, and the results of one iteration help in creating the next one. BO resembles the Random Search method in the sense that it samples a subset of hyperparameter combinations; however, they differ in the way in which each combination is chosen. BO views the hyperparameter tuning process as the optimisation of a black-box function. The function to be optimised is the model’s final prediction score.

It is called Bayesian because it uses the famous “Bayes’ theorem”, which states (simplifying) that the posterior probability of a model (or, in this case, a set of hyperparameters) M given evidence (or data, or observations) E is proportional to the likelihood of E given M multiplied by the prior probability of M :

$$P(M|E) \propto P(E|M) P(M)$$

The prior represents our belief about the space of possible objective functions. The posterior captures our updated beliefs about the unknown objective function. The model used to approximate the objective function is called a *surrogate model*. A number of surrogate models for Bayesian optimisation are in use, but perhaps the most common one is the Gaussian Process (GP). First, a few hyperparameter combinations are randomly chosen and tested. These randomly selected hyperparameters’ values are then used to produce the first model of the objective function. Once a first draft of the model is obtained, there are two methods to choose the next combination: one can either choose a value close to the highest obtained value, where performance is likely to increase, or one can explore another subset of the hyperparameter search space, where another maximum could be found. This way, a balance is found between exploration and exploitation.

This is obtained through the second essential ingredient in BO, the *acquisition function*. This function "looks" at the surrogate model and determines which areas of the domain of the objective function are worth exploiting and which are worth exploring. Accordingly, in areas where the objective function f is optimal

or areas that have not been previously researched, the acquisition function assumes a high value. On the contrary, where f is suboptimal or in areas that have already been sampled, its value is small. By finding the x that maximises the acquisition function, we identify the next best guess for f to try. By maximising the acquisition function instead of the objective function itself, whose analytic form is unknown, the process is much easier and much less expensive.

The most simple acquisition function there is, and the one used in this work, is the Upper Confidence Bound (UCB). It contains explicit exploitation $\mu(x)$ and exploration $\sigma(x)$ terms:

$$a(x; \lambda) = \mu(x) + \lambda\sigma(x).$$

The exploitation vs exploration tradeoff is straightforward and easy to tune via the parameter λ . Concretely, UCB is a weighted sum of the expected performance captured by $\mu(x)$ of the Gaussian Process, and of the uncertainty $\sigma(x)$, captured by the standard deviation of the GP. When λ is small, BO will favor solutions that are expected to be high-performing, i.e., have high $\mu(x)$. On the contrary, when λ is large, BO rewards the exploration of currently uncharted areas in the search space.

Applying Bayesian optimisation with the Gaussian Process fitness function over a data set of size n has a time complexity of $O(n^3)$ and space complexity of $O(n^2)$ [83]. Its advantage is that it does not sample each combination in the search space, as Grid Search does, and, at the same time, it proceeds in a more systematic manner than Random Search.

In Figure 3.12, an example of using Bayesian optimisation on a toy 1D design problem, taken from [84]. The figures show a Gaussian process (GP) approximation of the objective function over three iterations. The figure also shows the acquisition function in the lower green-shaded plots. The acquisition is high where the GP predicts a high objective (exploitation) and where the prediction uncertainty is high (exploration) — areas with both attributes are sampled first. Note that the area on the far left remains unsampled, as while it has high uncertainty, it is (correctly) predicted to offer little improvement over the highest observation.

Figure 3.12: Example of Bayesian Optimisation procedure to maximise a function over 3 iterations.

For the aforementioned five architectures, the hyperparameters that were tuned were:

Units. The dimensionality of the output y_t , i.e. of the hidden state of a layer.

Dropout rate. The frequency at which a layer randomly sets input units to 0 at each step during training time, to prevent overfitting.

Learning rate. How much to update the model weights and, consequently, how fast the model learns on the training data set.

Kernel size. In CNN-based architectures, the size of the kernel to use in each convolutional layer.

Chapter 4

The data set

A data set that consists of measurements from 156 zones in a WDS was considered. A *measurement zone* is a node of the water supply network.

For each measurement zone, the examined data consists of a flow rate value (called "portate" or "portata" in all the plots), measured in litres per second (l/s), and a pressure value (called "pressione"), measured in bars, both sampled every 6 minutes.

Both flow rate and pressure are continuous attributes that can assume negative values. In addition, different sensors can have very different value ranges for the two attributes. For example, in the time series in Figure 4.1 the flow rate ranges from 0 (probably a sensor error) to 50. In other series, the flow rate can reach over 250 and go as low as -32 .

The data set can be divided into two measurement campaigns. The first one is composed of 122 sensors, whose measurement values were collected over a span of two months. The second campaign consists of the remaining 34 sensors. In contrast with the first campaign, their values were taken over the span of a little over two years.

Figure 4.1: Example of a time series provided from a sensor on a measurement zone of the water supply network.

4.1 Correlation

In exploring a data set, it is important to discover whether a correlation exists between its variables, in this case flow rate and pressure.

Since a normal, Gaussian distribution cannot be assumed in either variable, the tool of choice to do so is the Spearman's rank correlation coefficient.

The Spearman's rank correlation coefficient, commonly represented as ρ , is the non-parametric version of the Pearson product-moment correlation. It measures the direction of the monotonic relationship between your two variables rather than the strength and direction of their linear relationship, which is what Pearson's correlation determines. It is calculated as the ratio between the covariance of the rank of two variables and the product of their standard deviations. In such a way, the result always has a value between -1 and 1 .

Given paired data $\{(x_1, y_1), \dots, (x_n, y_n)\}$, consisting of n pairs, they need to be converted to ranks $R(X_i), R(Y_i)$ and ρ is computed as:

$$\rho = \frac{\text{cov}(R(X)R(Y))}{\sigma_{R(X)} \sigma_{R(Y)}}$$

where $\text{cov}(R(X)R(Y))$ is the covariance of the rank variables, and $\sigma_{R(X)}, \sigma_{R(Y)}$ are the standard deviations of the rank variables.

Its maximum value, $\rho = 1$ corresponds to the case when there's a monotonically increasing function between the two features. In other words, larger x values correspond to larger y values and vice versa.

Its minimum value, $\rho = -1$, corresponds to the case when there's a monotonically decreasing function between x and y . That is, larger x values correspond to smaller y values and vice versa.

Figure 4.2: Same time series as in Figure 4.1, normalised between 0 and 1. Here, the Spearman correlation coefficient is of -0.54 . The pressure is plotted inverted to highlight the inverse proportionality of the two values.

In the considered data set of 120 time series, the average Spearman's rank correlation coefficient between flow rate and pressure is -0.37 , with the 75th percentile being -0.17 . This indicates an inverse monotonic relationship between the two variables, as can be seen in Figure 4.2.

We can therefore expect to be able to identify some anomalies in cases where this correlation is broken.

4.2 Preprocessing

The data was provided as *.dat* files, one for flow rate and one for pressure, for each measurement zone. Each value was accompanied by its date and time of acquisition. Unfortunately, some data loss was to be expected since the considered data set was not artificially constructed but comes from real-world data measured from sensors often located in harsh environments.

Data loss is a permanent error condition in which information is destroyed. It often results from problems with the equipment's power supply or with the communication system between sensors and data loggers.

By not having part of the data of a sensor, training (or applying) a model can become problematic, since they work with discrete steps. To overcome the issue, data has to be reconstructed and the gaps filled. The easiest way to do so is by *linear interpolation*. This method uses linear polynomials to construct new data points within the range of a discrete set of known data points, which in this case are the last available data point before the loss and the first available after the loss. This way, there is a risk of introducing the concept of "garbage in, garbage out", for which incorrect or nonsense input data will produce a faulty output. However, using different, more complex techniques to reconstruct missing data points is out of the scope of this work, and would in any case just mitigate the issue without solving it from its root.

The safer path to follow is instead to just ignore all the series that presented some data loss, but this would have meant discarding most of the data set. To keep as much information as possible, instead of dropping the whole sensor series, only the windows containing a data loss were thrown away, keeping all the other ones.

4.2.1 Data normalisation

Data scaling is a recommended preprocessing step when working with many machine learning algorithms [85]. Machine learning models learn a mapping from input variables to an output variable. The scale and distribution of the

data drawn from the domain may be different for each variable, as they may have different units that, in turn, may mean the variables have different scales. Differences in the scales across input variables may increase the difficulty of the problem being modelled. An example of this is that large input values (e.g. a spread of hundreds or thousands of units) can result in a model that learns large weight values. A model with large weight values is often unstable, meaning that it may suffer from poor performance during learning and sensitivity to input values, resulting in higher generalisation error. Moreover, if a feature has a variance that is orders of magnitude larger than others, it might dominate the objective function and make the estimator unable to learn from other features correctly as expected.

A common transformation in machine learning is the *normalisation* which is a rescaling of the data from the original range so that all values are within the new range $[min, max]$.

$$z = \frac{X - X_{min}}{X_{max} - X_{min}} \cdot (max - min) + min.$$

In general, the new range is $[0, 1]$ and the good practice usage with normalisation and other scaling techniques is as follows:

1. Fit the scaler using available training data. For normalisation, this means the training data will be used to estimate the minimum and maximum observable values.
2. Apply the scale to training data. This means we can use the normalised data to train our model.
3. Apply the scale to testing data. This means we can prepare new data in the future on which we want to make predictions.

4.2.2 Feature engineering

Before proceeding to training the model, a key step is *feature engineering*. The feature engineering pipeline is the preprocessing steps that transform raw data into features that can be used in machine learning algorithms to improve their performance. The goal was to expose valid relationships between input features and the target variable to be predicted. The features computed from the time series where the following.

Holiday. Boolean which indicates if that data point was extracted during a public holiday in Italy.

Weekday. Day of the week, ranging from 0 being Monday to 6 being Sunday.

Month. Number of the month in the year, from 1 to 12.

Hour. Hour in the day, ranging from 0 to 23.

Difference. Difference of the value of the data point with the previous one, computed for both pressure and flow rate.

These all were later passed on to the models to learn from in order to improve the final prediction, lower the error and therefore increase accuracy in anomaly detection.

4.3 Sensor anomalies

Two different types of anomalies can be identified in the data provided by a water supply network, sensor anomalies and physical anomalies. Two different model training approaches were followed depending on the type of anomaly. Given that the provided data set did not have labelled anomalies, the detection was carried on in a semi-supervised manner, as introduced in Section 2.5.

A sensor anomaly is caused by a malfunction of one or more sensors and is not generally related to an abnormality in the water flow. Usually it is a point anomaly, or sequence of. For this reason, not much context is needed.

The way to identify it is as a break in the pattern for the variable whose sensor is failing, while the other sensor continues with normal behaviour. The odds of both of the sensors failing at the same time are very low but, in case it happens, the anomaly can still be identified as an interruption in the pattern, although there is a risk of marking it as a physical anomaly instead.

In Figure 4.3, an example of an anomaly in the pressure sensor is shown. The detected value, after staying relatively constant, repeatedly drops to a series of zeros, before returning to the previous constant positive range. There is a clear break in the pattern while the water flow sensor behaves normally, indicating a probable failure in the singular sensor.

Figure 4.3: Example of a sensor anomaly in the pressure sensor of a measurement zone in the water supply network.

In order to detect sensor anomalies, the training and testing of the models was performed on 1.5 months of "clean" data taken from all sensors available, identified by a field expert. This includes, and is limited to, all series without any sensor anomalies, or missing data points. The last 2 weeks of some series, both "clean" and with alleged anomalies, were then used to simulate a real-life application of the sensor anomaly detection model. In Figure 4.5, at the end of the chapter, a visual representation of the data set division.

While the time series of the first measurement campaign are already two months long, leaving no doubt as to which data is being used, the series from the second campaign are much longer. There, the aforementioned total of two months was taken from the most recent data of each series, leaving the rest to the physical anomaly detection model.

Since, as mentioned before, different time series have very different data scales, each series was normalised on its own, without confronting the values with the others in the data set. The reason behind this decision was that a sensor anomaly is identified solely by a change in the values, not by their magnitude.

Similarly, the window length L , introduced in Section 3.4, was kept small at a value of 10 points, corresponding to an hour of data. Since a sensor anomaly is mainly identified through the relationship between flow rate and pressure, the model did not need to learn long patterns as much as the dynamics between the two variables.

4.4 Physical anomalies

This kind of anomaly, in this context, is usually caused by one of two reasons. The first possible agent is a leak in the pipes, which can result from broken seals, corrosion, underground movements, high water pressure, intruding tree roots, and various other reasons. Leak detection is nowadays an important task for

water utilities, as leakages in water distribution systems increase economic costs significantly and create water resource shortages [86].

Other possible causes are a change in the users' demand or manoeuvring of valves in the network.

Figure 4.4: Example of a physical anomaly measured in a measurement zone in the water supply network.

In Figure 4.4, an example of a physical anomaly, confirmed by a field expert to have been generated by a scheduled suspension of water supply in the area due to extraordinary maintenance to the network. Both sensors simultaneously change their value range and break the pattern, as expected from an anomaly of this kind.

In order to detect physical anomalies, the training and testing of the models were done on the first year and a half of a series in the second measurement campaign. The following 6 months of available data were used for live simulation of both the sensor and the physical anomaly detection model on that same series. In Figure 4.5, a visual representation of the data set division is shown.

Figure 4.5: Visual representation of the studied data set's division for training and testing the prediction models, and for the live pipeline application simulation. "MC" stands for measurement campaign.

The training data was cleaned from data loss and sensor anomalies, the latter being the ones detected by a sensor anomaly detection model applied to the data, in order to prevent the "garbage in, garbage out" phenomenon. If their anomaly index values went over the threshold mentioned in Section 3.3 they were dropped, in order to allow for the model to learn on "clean" data and not assimilate any unwanted behaviour. Since the application of the physical anomaly model is on a series per time, each series was normalised on its own in the interval $[0, 1]$. The decision to use one model per series and not cluster all series together as for the sensor anomalies was motivated by the importance of magnitude in data for this application. For the same reason, the window length L was increased to 240 data points, representing a full day of data. In this case, the model needed to learn long patterns, and water consumption shows a daily periodicity.

Chapter 5

Results

In the following chapter, the results obtained with the previously introduced methods are presented and discussed.

The first section consists of an evaluation of the best performing architecture for the prediction phase of the anomaly detection process. Following that, three examples of the anomaly model applied to different measurement zones of the WSN are shown.

5.1 Model architecture selection

The architecture used to carry out the prediction phase of the anomaly detection process was chosen using the division introduced in Section 4.3 for the training and testing of models for the detection of sensor anomalies.

Considering as the metric of choice the mean of the Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE), introduced in Subsection 3.2.1, calculated between the true values and the predictions, the models were ranked by it and the one with the lowest error was chosen to complete the task. The obtained results are reported in Table 5.1, where the grey row highlights the best-performing model.

Architecture	MAPE	Time	Epochs
LSTM	5.14916557	305.93501710	2
GRU	5.04096572	2480.80576539	17
CNN-LSTM	4.90278151	513.83259034	3
TCN	5.01339896	8891.60881090	20
Transformer	5.27668759	5250.34775924	45

Table 5.1: Prediction performance results of the five considered architectures for the sensor anomaly model.

Each architecture got its hyperparameters tuned and was then trained for 50 epochs. Then, for each model, the epoch with the lowest MAPE was extracted and the model fitted again until that iteration. The trained model was then saved to make it available and ready to use in future applications, avoiding the hustle of retraining it before every use.

As highlighted by Table 5.1, most models had very similar performances. However, CNN-LSTM managed to obtain a lower error than its competitors, and to do so in only 3 epochs. All hyperparameters were tuned to the lowest possible setting:

- kernel size: 2,
- units: 8,
- dropout: 0.0,
- learning rate: 0.01.

The worst-performing architecture was the Transformer, which also took more than double the epochs to achieve this result.

Considering the longer window and the known potential of some of the considered architectures when dealing with them, it was deemed appropriate to search for a new architecture and new hyperparameters for the detection of physical anomalies. Due to the large amount of data available from the second measurement campaign to train the physical anomaly model, a different approach was adopted from earlier, where instead of training on all available series, only a fourth were considered. This subset was created to be as representative of the whole set as possible, in terms of patterns and magnitude of values.

Keeping MAPE as the reference metric, the results are reported in Table 5.2, where the grey row highlights the best-performing model.

The same procedure of tuning and training was used. However, unlike what was done for the one for sensor anomalies, the model was saved untrained. This way, it could be trained on a specific measurement zone each time it was needed. The results are reported in the following Table (5.2).

Architecture	MAPE	Time	Epochs
LSTM	6.01489211	7802.82018947	22
GRU	7.11273905	5468.92840173	15
CNN-LSTM	8.24904718	5843.75120031	9
TCN	7.25432896	11891.01736632	18
Transformer	7.19992811	9045.19825641	26

Table 5.2: Prediction performance results of the five considered architectures for the physical anomaly model.

As highlighted in Table 5.2, LSTM outperformed the other architectures. This was expected, because of LSTMs’ ability to learn long-term patterns by solving the vanishing gradient problem.

The hyperparameters were tuned in the following way:

- units: 16,
- dropout: 0,
- learning rate: 0.001.

5.2 Model application

Two anomaly detection models, one for the sensor anomalies and one for the physical anomalies, were applied in sequence for each measurement zone of the water distribution network. Then, three measurement zones were randomly selected between the ones in which the model detected some anomalies.

The output for each anomaly type will be a plot of the time series with the associated anomaly index τ . In all plots, the pink areas are the zones of data loss where the values have been reconstructed with linear interpolation.

If the same data points were marked as both sensor and physical anomalies, the sensor anomaly model was given priority, since if a value is measured wrongly by the sensor, it cannot be considered valid in any way, least of all as a physical anomaly.

5.2.1 Measurement zone A

The first measurement zone to be considered is the following.

Figure 5.1: Plot of the two sensors in measurement zone A.

By passing the time series through the first step of the anomaly detection model, aimed at identifying sensor anomalies, the outputs are the plots in Figure 5.2.

Figure 5.2: Plots of the two series of measurement zone A with their respective sensor anomaly index, each with a zoom on a downward peak. Above the pressure values, below the flow rate.

The model detects two peaks that, from the zoomed squares in the same figure, appear to be point outliers. For this reason, and since their anomalous behaviour does not reflect on the other sensor, the model marks them as sensor anomalies. These were later confirmed by a field expert. The rest of the series

does not present any point outliers, and the model doesn't raise any warnings. It is important to highlight how even if the anomalies were evident, the model did not have any clue as to their presence or location, and marked them as such by learning from the data. This makes the anomaly detection model automatic in every aspect.

Continuing on with the second and last step of the anomaly detection process, the physical anomaly model is applied to the same series. In Figure 5.3, the output.

Figure 5.3: Plots of the two series in measurement zone A with their respective physical anomaly index. Above the pressure values, below the flow rate.

Nothing is flagged as anomaly by the model.

5.2.2 Measurement zone B

The second measurement zone where the anomaly model found some anomalies was the following.

Figure 5.4: Plot of the two sensors in measurement zone B.

From the plotted time series a curious behaviour can be observed at the very beginning in the pressure values, in purple. On the other hand, the flow rate doesn't mirror these variations in any way, suggesting the nature of this anomaly to regard the sensor itself. This is confirmed in Figure 5.5, where a zoom can be seen on the examined interval, and the sensor anomaly index oftentimes reaches high values.

Figure 5.5: Plots of the two series in measurement zone B with their respective sensor anomaly index, and zoom on the initial perturbations. Above the pressure values, below the flow rate.

Contrastingly, the sensor anomaly detection model doesn't mark any outliers in the flow rate values. The sensory nature of this anomaly was later confirmed by a field expert, who pinpointed its cause to a complex hydraulic system. In short, the sensor works well when the pipe is full, measuring the right values, while it fails when the pipe is under-filled and works through gravity instead of pressure.

As confirmed by a field expert, this measurement zone did not have any physical anomalies in this time frame. The wide peaks present in the flow rate series are again due to the complex hydraulic systems but completely normal, and the model, correctly, did not identify them as outliers (Figure 5.6).

Figure 5.6: Plots of the two series in measurement zone B with their respective physical anomaly index. Above the pressure values, below the flow rate.

The sensor anomalies at the beginning of the series for the pressure sensor were also identified as physical outliers. However, as mentioned at the beginning of this Section, if a value is measured wrongly by the sensor it cannot be considered valid in any way, least of all a physical anomaly.

5.2.3 Measurement zone C

This last measurement zone is located in a pumping station placed on an elevated point of the WDS.

Figure 5.7: Plot of the two sensors in measurement zone C.

By applying the sensor anomaly model, the output is reported in Figure 5.8. The model detects two peaks and marks them as slightly anomalous in the flow rate sensor, while the related values in the pressure time series have a low anomaly index, nowhere near the threshold.

Figure 5.8: Plots of the two series in measurement zone C with their respective sensor anomaly index. Above the pressure values, below the flow rate.

As mentioned beforehand, the failure of two sensors at the same time is highly improbable. In fact, when applying as the next step the physical anomaly detection model, the two peaks are heavily marked as such, as expected. This

can be seen in Figure 5.9.

Figure 5.9: Plots of the two series in measurement zone C with their respective physical anomaly index. Above the pressure values, below the flow rate.

Since the sensor anomaly index values are low while the physical anomaly index values are much higher and decisive in both sensors, the points are marked as the latter.

These two were in fact physical anomalies later confirmed by a field expert, caused by some variations in the activation of the pumps. Instead, the many flow rate peaks detected as mild physical anomalies towards the end of the studied time period were probably caused by an increased water demand from the network near the measurement zone.

Chapter 6

Conclusions and future work

Water is a common good and a limited and strategic resource that needs to be protected and used in a sustainable way, in terms of both quality and quantity. Because of the pressure on water resources caused by the combination of demographic evolution, the general trend of increasing urbanisation and the impact of climate change, water operators face a challenge in water management. The demand should be sustainable and efficient, water leakages should be identified and managed properly, and the quality of the water supplied to the customers should be kept under observation.

In addition, accessible and high-quality freshwater is a limited and highly variable resource, with over two billion people around the world without access to drinking water and basic water services. New strategies are needed for water conservation, improving water management, and enhancing the water supply systems' resiliency, and saving water leaked from a water distribution system represents a solution. Timely detection of leakage events provides opportunities for water companies to not only save water but also money and energy.

The water industry of the future is expected to be smart and resource-efficient, with networked, intelligent systems helping make better use of energy, avoid unnecessary water losses, and optimise the consumption of resources. Some front-runner water utilities have already put into practise new digital technologies such as smart sensors and advanced data analytics models that provide detailed data, allowing deeper insights into water availability, quality, and use.

In particular, many water distribution networks are continuously monitored through installed sensors that measure hydraulic parameters (e.g., pressure, flow rate, users' consumption) and water quality parameters (e.g., chlorine concentration, pH, temperature). The continuous monitoring allows the

collection of raw data to be used in multiple engineering applications, such as leakage control, the calculation of water balances, the evaluation of WSS key performance indicators, the development and calibration of hydraulic models in terms of nodal demands and pipe roughness coefficients, and water demand reconstruction and forecast.

Performing leakage control and detecting changes in customer water demand or manoeuvring in the network can be summarised as physical anomaly detection. To perform this task, the time series of flow rate and pressure need to be analysed and passed through an anomaly detection model. The objective of this thesis was to provide this anomaly detection model, based on semi-supervised deep learning methods. In this model, first sensor anomalies and malfunctions need to be identified to avoid the "garbage in, garbage out" phenomenon. Then, physical anomalies such as leakages can be pinpointed by the model and tackled by sector experts.

This model also finds an application in the step of data cleaning for engineering tasks that support the water distribution network, which require well-processed, reliable time series without anomalies.

As future work, it would be ideal to scale the anomaly detection model to consider more than one measurement zone at a time. By considering a network of sensors and analysing their measurements while taking into account the spatial-temporal correlation between them, leakage detection becomes more accurate, due to the possibility to estimate water loss between sensors and variations in consumption in each district.

Another improvement to the physical anomaly detection model would be, instead of training it series by series, to do so on clusters of measurement zones, grouped together not by topology but through correlation and value magnitude.

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Appendix A

Implementation

All the techniques and methods mentioned in the thesis were implemented in Python. Python is a computer programming language often used to build websites and software, automate tasks, and conduct data analysis. It is a general-purpose language, which means it is designed to be used in a range of applications, including data science, software and web development, and automation. This versatility, along with its beginner-friendliness, has made it one of the most-used programming languages today.

Given the large amount of data to be handled, running the programs on a personal computer would have resulted troublesome in terms of memory and speed. For this reason, a more powerful machine was needed. All computations were carried out on Rosetta [87], a science platform for resource-intensive, interactive data analysis which runs user tasks as software containers. These support custom and user-defined software packages, libraries and environments, including a complete remote desktop and Jupyter notebooks [88], a web-based interactive computational environment which supports various languages, including Python.

A.1 Python packages

Python relies heavily on *modules*, a Python file with reusable, importable code. Several modules combined are called a *package*. During the development of the code supporting this thesis, various packages have been exploited. The following list comprehends a few fundamental ones.

Timeseria*. An object-oriented time series processing library which aims at

*<https://github.com/sarusso/Timeseria>

making it easy to manipulate time series data and to build statistical and machine learning models on top of it.

Tensorflow. An open source software library for high performance numerical computation [89]. Its flexible architecture allows easy deployment of computation across a variety of platforms (CPUs, GPUs), and from desktops to clusters of servers to mobile and edge devices Originally developed by researchers and engineers from the Google Brain team within Google's AI organisation, it comes with strong support for machine learning and deep learning.

Keras [90] is a deep-learning framework acting as an interface to the Tensorflow library. It was used to build the architectures, train and evaluate them.

Keras tuner. A scalable hyperparameter optimisation framework that solves the pain points of hyperparameter search [91].

Keras nlp. An API for building Natural Language Processing (NLP) models within the Keras ecosystem [92]. It was used to exploit their pre-made Transformer layers, saving a lot of time and effort.

Tcn. Keras implementation of a TCN architecture [93]. Again, it saved time and effort by not having to implement it from scratch.

Multiprocessing. A package that supports spawning processes to fully leverage multiple processors on a given machine. Parallelising the workload was a paramount task in order to make the anomaly detection system efficient and applicable in real-life scenarios.

Joblib. A set of tools to provide lightweight pipelining in Python, optimised to be fast and robust on large data. It is in part based on the *multiprocessing* package.